

Whispering in Shadows: Reconstructing Identity through Environment and Indigeneity

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Abstract: *Through my research paper, I intend to take issues of identity, indigeneity and environment pertaining to Jeannette Armstrong's *Whispering in Shadows*. Armstrong, a Native Canadian writer from Okaangan Valley puts forth her worries towards the preservation of Nature and its resources through the character of Penny Jackson. Penny Jackson, the protagonist of the novel, considers the economic policy of globalization to be the major reason for the plight of the natives in Canada, U. S. A. and the likes. Colonialism and subjugation, which lasted for more than 500 years, combined with the denial of political, economic, and cultural freedom, resulted in the contamination of indigenous communities ancestral lands and the subsequent genocide of entire populations. Using literature as a platform for activism represents a new opportunity for radical change as Armstrong necessitates a confrontation with the questions of Identity, Indigeneity, Environment and cultural hegemony.*

Keywords: Environment; Indigenous community; Identity; Land; Native Canada.

Introduction

Jeannette Christine Armstrong, born in 1948 is a Canadian author, born and grew up on Penticton Indian reserve in British Columbia's Okanagan Valley. Armstrong stresses on the themes of language, identity and environment that are inherent in the

wholeness of the Okanagan community. Her literary works aim to express her feelings about the symbiosis of land, language, and community, while also generating and perpetuating a creative process that benefits more than one person. She is also an advocate for Indigenous people's rights and focuses her work on the revitalization of Indigenous communities and environment.

The environment includes everything that makes up our surroundings, including air, water, land, plants, and animals, and its quality has an impact on our ability to live on the planet. Extensive research has been conducted in recent decades to examine how people affect the environment. Air pollution, deforestation, acid rain, and other environmental threats, according to reports, are man-made calamities that will eventually take a severe toll on both humans and non-human organisms. This paper examines the ecosystem of Canada's native reservations, which has been harmed by colonisation and capital imperialism. Armstrong, in her works, shows how native lifestyle and belief system is in harmony with Nature and exhibits respect and care for Earth with the flora and fauna in its lap.

Cheryll Glotfelty defines Ecocriticism in introduction to *The Ecocriticism Reader* (1996)

“What...is Ecocriticism? Simply put, Ecocriticism is the study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment. Just as Feminist Criticism examines language and literature from a gender-conscious perspective, and Marxist Criticism brings an awareness of modes of production and economic class to literary studies.” (168)

The story portrayed by renowned Okanagan author Jeannette Armstrong traces the life of a young Native woman on a reserve who is exposed to pesticides while working as a fruit picker in the Okanagan Valley. It provides a glimpse into the complexities of the contemporary life and psyche of Aboriginal people. The novel conveys an important environmental theme and insights into the future as well. It follows the life of Okanagan painter Penny, who

has been diagnosed with cancer after working as a fruit picker in the Okanagan Valley and exposing herself to pesticides. In the novel, we get a glimpse of what it is like to live and think like an Aboriginal person in the present day. An essential ecological theme is conveyed in the novel. After witnessing injustice as an Okanagan Indian, Penny Jackson sets out on a national and international journey in search of a path to self-discovery. Penny, like Jeannette Armstrong, responds to the real threat to Native communities by erasing their identity in favour of whiteness at the expense of nativeness through activism and art. One of Jeannette Armstrong's main motivations for writing this novel was to resist white oppression and support the harmed communities. She uses literature as a form of resistance and a tool for decolonization. The novel depicts complex modernization and globalization system, which governs modern society, and the complex indigenous traditions that eventually return us to our own mother earth.

Rob Nixon, a professor in Humanities and the Environment at Princeton writes about social and environmental movements. It is because of Nixon's assessment of the devastating social, cultural, spiritual, and economic effects of such acts on Indigenous peoples whose definition of self and family are grounded in their connections to and relationships with the land that further that Nixon conceptualises environmental degradation as well as the displacements that it creates similar to acts of war.

In the words of Rob Nixon in *Slow Violence and Environmentalism of the Poor*, published in 2011,

“By slow violence I mean a violence that occurs gradually and out of sight, a violence of delayed destruction that is dispersed across time and space.... We need, I believe, to engage a different kind of violence, a violence that is neither spectacular nor instantaneous, but rather incremental and accretive, its calamitous repercussions playing out across a range of temporal scales.” (119)

Cheryl Suzack and Shari M. Huhndorf argue in *Indigenous Women and Feminism: Politics, Activism and Culture* that:

“Although Indigenous feminism is a nascent field of scholarly inquiry, it has arisen from histories of women’s activism and culture that have aimed to combat gender discrimination, secure social justice for Indigenous women, and counter their social erasure and marginalization – endeavors that fall arguably under the rubric of feminism, despite Indigenous women’s fraught relationship with the term and with mainstream feminist movements.” (20)

This expansive collection delves into the political, social, and cultural landscapes, emphasizing the contributions of indigenous women both historically and in their present roles as thinkers and activists. Writers who view literature as a tool for social good often embed activism within their work. Employing literature as a means of advocacy opens new pathways for meaningful and transformative change.

According to Armstrong, contemporary cities like Los Angeles, where a never-ending string of ultramodern skyscrapers completely blocks out any view of a clear blue sky, are horrendous places to live. Suffocating views of concrete jungles like this make environmentalist Penny Jackson want to scream and run away in terror. A call to return to Aboriginal localism is made in *Whispering in Shadows* by Penny’s commitment to resisting globalisation through her art and activism work. Penny makes herself heard on the basis of activities she indulges in as well as holds a diverse view on various topics ranging from colonialism, globalisation, modernism. She uses her activism not only as a strategy to combat globalisation but also to empower indigenous communities as well as indigenous women.

The protagonist, who is raised on a Native American reservation and has grown up with some traditional knowledge and a fondness for colour and art. One of the world’s most successful artists, a single mother of three who became an internationalist visiting indigenous peoples and relating their situation to her own, becomes ill from taking on so much of the pain of the world, and finally

returns to help preserve and renew her own tribe's traditions and solidarity.

Penny's grandmother, who has a deep understanding of the Okanagan philosophy, is a wise woman. It is Tupa's role to embody Okanagan cultural collaboration's values and practises, and she has shaped the protagonist's attitude and spiritual nourishment.

Land and individual human relationships with the land are intertwined familial dependences because it carries meaning and identity that encompasses culture, social, personal and communal existence. Because of the devastation caused by globalisation, reconnecting to the land provides a strong foundation for healing and preserving cultural identity.

Communities based on Native cultures that see women as part of the land are directly impacted by land degradation, as well as discrimination and injustice related to a lack of respect for sacred traditional practises, according to these cultures. However, despite the fact that Penny's indigenous identity is not considered authentic to indiginity, she tends to preserve her own identity and that of Okanagan, which is spiritually and culturally linked to her indigenous self-identity.

Another lens to this perspective is Penny's obsession with colours, this can be interpreted as a metaphor for the Natural world, which is why Penny has such a maniacal obsession with colours and why no one around her understands her. It implies that the Material world views the Natural world as abnormal or incomprehensible. As a result, for Penny, painting is a metaphorical escape from the material world, where she finds peace, solace, and comfort in ways that others cannot comprehend.

In the opinion of Penny's friend Roberta, who is unable to comprehend Penny's interest in colour and art, "Why don't you think of normal stuff, like how that cool guy Michael has a new car." (Armstrong 9)

Aside from preserving cultural legacies, the effort is also aimed at safeguarding nature from Western materialistic and capitalistic influences. Nature takes on new meanings for these people, even though the settlers have done everything in their power to remove them from their homes. Indigenous people and settlers are contrasted in the text in terms of their relationship to nature. For example, an activist at a camp on five valley coast of Vancouver island, Jim wonders why the indigenous people wouldn't think of making money from their lands if they were given full control. Penny responds in the affirmative.

Armstrong says, "It seems to me what you just said is the real problem. They haven't devastated any of their lands in the thousands of years of living here. Why would they do it now? I don't think there's enough research on the fact that native people understand real sustainability and practice it even on the small reserves left of their homelands." (109)

Land and people are, according to Simon Ortiz who is an American Native writer and is an active participant of second wave of Native American Renaissance says, "one and the same essential matter of Existence." When it comes to Penny's understanding of her connection to the land, her deepening of ties with her family, and even the inheriting of traditional customs, history, and philosophy, the self-sustaining culture of farming that is practised on the land has a lot to do with it.

Armstrong in "Land Speaking" says,

"All my elders say that it is land that holds all knowledge of life and death and is a constant teacher. It is said in Okanagan that the land constantly speaks. Not to learn its language is to die. We survived and thrived by listening intently to its teachings—to its language—and then inventing human words to retell its stories to our succeeding generations—in the sense, all indigenous people's languages are generated by a precise geography and arise from it."

Recognizing that Native people stand at a pivot point at this time in history, each having the responsibility of deciding for descendants how their world shall be affected and what shall be their heritage.

Conclusion

The turn to voicing indigenous provides an opportunity to imagine more just ‘plantation futures’ in an era of environmental degradation.

Eco-lit needs to delve deeper into portrayals of how environmental degradation leads to human agony, suffering and displacements; how citizens turn into refugees within their own country; how economic and political exploitation turn human life upside down and jeopardise the environment, thereby making it unsuitable for life in future. But it needs to be done as literature, as human stories of subtlety, not just the sterile badgering of activism.” Jeannette Armstrong, envisioned “the survival of what is human in an inhuman world” and has proposed a possibility of a new ending to the story. As Native woman writer she locates the roots of the degradation of land on the basis of insensitivity and callousness in Canada’s colonial history, she also strives to find the means of changing the system which perpetuates the oppression of land.

In the words of Nicanor Parra, a poet from Chile, who claims himself to an anti- poet,

“The mistake we made was in the thinking
that the earth belonged to us
when the fact of the matter is
we’re the ones who belong to the earth.”

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